

On the Security and Safety of AbU Systems

(Supplementary Material)

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Technical report with the supplementary material of the paper “On the Security and Safety of AbU Systems” [1].

1 Proofs of Section 5

We recall (and generalize) here the definition of the system initialization function, that takes a set of states, a set of rules and a set of pools and it returns a AbU system, with the specified rules, states and pools. Formally, given $\bar{R} = \{R_1, \dots, R_n\}$, $\bar{\Sigma} = \{\Sigma_1, \dots, \Sigma_n\} \in \text{comp}(\bar{R})$ and $\bar{\Theta} = \{\Theta_1, \dots, \Theta_n\}$, we define $\text{sys}(\bar{R}, \bar{\Sigma}, \bar{\Theta})$ as: $R_1 \langle \Sigma_1, \Theta_1 \rangle \parallel \dots \parallel R_n \langle \Sigma_n, \Theta_n \rangle$. When all pools are empty, we just write $\text{sys}(\bar{R}, \bar{\Sigma})$ in place of $\text{sys}(\bar{R}, \bar{\Sigma}, \{\emptyset, \dots, \emptyset\})$.

We also recall the notion of L-level twin of a AbU rules set $\bar{R} = \{R_1, \dots, R_n\}$, i.e., the rules set \bar{R}_L where all resources in $\text{evset}(\bar{R})$ are substituted in \bar{R} with their primed version. Here, the H-level events set of \bar{R} is $\text{evset}(\bar{R}) \triangleq \bigcup_{1 \leq i \leq n} \text{evset}(R_i)$, with $\text{evset}(\text{rule}_1 \dots \text{rule}_m) \triangleq \bigcup_{1 \leq j \leq m} \text{evset}(\text{rule}_j)$ and $\text{evset}(x_1 \dots x_k \triangleright \text{act}, \text{task}) \triangleq \{x_i \mid i \in [1..k] \wedge \mathcal{P}(x_i) = \text{H}\}$.

Proof of Theorem 5.1. We prove here the soundness of the proposed *security* verification mechanism, namely that if the Alg. 1 marks a AbU system as secure then the system satisfies the (presence-sensitive) noninterference of Def. 4.4.

Before going in the detail of the proof, we need a preliminary result and an auxiliary definition. Indeed, it is easy to note that Alg. 1 is not affected by resources renaming.

Proposition 1.1. *Consider a AbU rules set $\{R\}$ and its L-level twin $\{R_L\}$. We have that $\text{IFRules}(R) = \text{false} \iff \text{IFRules}(R_L) = \text{false}$.*

Furthermore, we need to define an equivalence relation between rules sets, basically saying that a rules set and its L-level twin are equivalent, and vice versa. In particular, the rules sets \bar{R} and \bar{R}' are equivalent when \bar{R}' is the L-level twin of \bar{R} or \bar{R} is the L-level twin of \bar{R}' .

Definition 1.1 (L-level twin equivalence). *Given two AbU rules sets \bar{R} and \bar{R}' , we say that \bar{R} and \bar{R}' are L-level twin equivalent, written $\bar{R} \stackrel{\text{H}}{\approx} \bar{R}'$, when:*

$$\bar{R}' = \bar{R}_L \vee \bar{R} = \bar{R}'_L$$

Finally, we need an equivalence between execution pools, saying that two pools are equal, except for updates containing renamed resources. We say that two updates are *primed equivalent* when they are identical or when they differ only for primed resources. For instance, $(l_1, 3)(l_2, 1)$ and $(l_1, 3)(l_2, 1)$ are primed equivalent, $(h_1, 3)(l_2, 1)$ and $(h'_1, 3)(l_2, 1)$ are primed equivalent, but $(l_1, 3)(l_2, 1)$ and $(h_1, 3)(l_2, 1)$ are not primed equivalent.

Definition 1.2 (Primed equivalence). *Given two AbU execution pools Θ_1 and Θ_2 , we say that Θ_1 and Θ_2 are primed equivalent, written $\Theta_1 \dot{=} \Theta_2$, when: for each upd in Θ_1 there exists upd' in Θ_2 such that upd and upd' are primed equivalent; and for each upd in Θ_2 there exists upd' in Θ_1 such that upd and upd' are primed equivalent.*

We can trivially extend the previous definition to sets of execution pools, and we abuse notation using the same symbol $\dot{=}$ to denote primed equivalence for pools and sets of pools.

Theorem 5.1 (Soundness for Security)

Proof. Let $\bar{R} = \{R_1, \dots, R_n\}$ and R be the list comprising all rules of all elements in $\{R_1, \dots, R_n\}$. Assume that $\text{IFRules}(R) = \text{false}$, then we have to prove that for all $\bar{\Sigma} \in \text{comp}(\bar{R})$ and $\bar{\Sigma}' \in \text{comp}(\bar{R}_L)$ such that $\bar{\Sigma} \equiv_L \bar{\Sigma}'$, we have that $\text{sys}(\bar{R}, \bar{\Sigma}) \approx_{H_L} \text{sys}(\bar{R}_L, \bar{\Sigma}')$, where h_L maps labels of the form T and $(x_1, v_1) \dots (x_k, v_k) \triangleright T$, with $\prod_{i \in [1..n]} \mathcal{P}(x_i) = H$, to $*$; maps labels of the form $(x_1, v_1) \dots (x_k, v_k) \triangleright T$, with $\prod_{i \in [1..n]} \mathcal{P}(x_i) = L$, to $(x_1, v_1) \dots (x_k, v_k)|_L$; and maps labels of the form $\text{upd} \blacktriangleright T$ to $\text{upd} \blacktriangleright T$. Let \mathcal{R} be the following binary and symmetric relation over AbU systems:

$$\mathcal{R} \triangleq \left\{ (\text{sys}(\bar{R}_1, \bar{\Sigma}_1, \bar{\Theta}_1), \text{sys}(\bar{R}_2, \bar{\Sigma}_2, \bar{\Theta}_2)) \left| \begin{array}{l} \bar{R}_1 \stackrel{H}{\approx} \bar{R}_2 \wedge \bar{\Sigma}_1 \in \text{comp}(\bar{R}_1) \wedge \\ \bar{\Sigma}_2 \in \text{comp}(\bar{R}_2) \wedge \bar{\Sigma}_1 \equiv_L \bar{\Sigma}_2 \wedge \\ \text{IFRules}(R_1) = \text{false} \wedge \\ \text{IFRules}(R_2) = \text{false} \wedge \\ \bar{\Theta}_1 \dot{=} \bar{\Theta}_2 \end{array} \right. \right\}$$

where R_1 and R_2 are the lists comprising all rules of all elements in \bar{R}_1 and \bar{R}_2 , respectively. Note that, given two generic rules sets \bar{R} and \bar{R}' , we have that $\bar{R} \stackrel{H}{\approx} \bar{R}'$ implies $\text{IFRules}(R) = \text{false}$ iff $\text{IFRules}(R') = \text{false}$ (due to Prop. 5.1 and Prop. 1.1). By definition, $(\text{sys}(\bar{R}, \bar{\Sigma}), \text{sys}(\bar{R}_L, \bar{\Sigma}')) \in \mathcal{R}$, so we have to prove that \mathcal{R} is a AbU hiding bisimulation, parametric on h_L .

Let $(S_a, S_b) \in \mathcal{R}$ and $S_a \xrightarrow{\alpha} S'_a$, for some AbU system label α . We have to show that there exists a system S'_b such that $S_b \xrightarrow{\alpha} S'_b$, with $(S'_a, S'_b) \in \mathcal{R}$. Note that, since AbU rules do not syntactically change during execution, we have that the rules set of S_a , say \bar{R}_a , is the same of the rules set of S'_a , say \bar{R}'_a . This, in turn, implies that $\text{IFRules}(R'_a)$, where R'_a is the list comprising all rules of all elements in \bar{R}'_a (the same applies for S_b and S'_b). The fact that $\bar{R}'_a \stackrel{H}{\approx} \bar{R}_b$ is trivial. In a similar way, if the set of states of S_a , say $\bar{\Sigma}_a$, is compatible with

\overline{R}_a , then also the set of states of S'_a , say $\overline{\Sigma}'_a$, is compatible with \overline{R}_a' (the same applies for S_b and S'_b). Hence, we just have to prove that there exists S'_b such that $S_b \xrightarrow{\alpha}_H S'_b$, $\overline{\Sigma}'_a \equiv_L \overline{\Sigma}'_b$ and $\overline{\Theta}'_a \equiv_L \overline{\Theta}'_b$, where $\overline{\Theta}'_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}'_b$ are the sets of execution pools of S'_a and S'_b , respectively. The proof proceeds by case analysis on the label α .

Case $\alpha = \text{upd} \blacktriangleright T$. This label can be only generated by an application of the rule (STEP) of the AbU systems semantics (Fig. 1), where one of the nodes in S_a has applied the rule (INPUT) of the AbU node semantics (Fig. 1). Let $\overline{\Sigma}_a = \{\Sigma_{a,1}, \dots, \Sigma_{a,n}\}$ and $\text{upd} = (x_1, v_1) \dots (x_k, v_k)$. Suppose that the input has been performed by the i^{th} node, with $i \in [1..n]$. By definition of (INPUT), we have that $\overline{\Sigma}'_a = \overline{\Sigma}_a[\Sigma'_{a,i}/\Sigma_{a,i}]$, with $\Sigma'_{a,i} = \Sigma_{a,i}[v_1/x_1 \dots v_k/x_k]$. However, an input denotes a modification of the resources made by an external entity. Thus, this label does not depend on the actual system and can always be performed both by S_a and S_b (we have to maintain fairness, i.e., external inputs have to be sent to both systems). Note that \overline{R}_a and \overline{R}_b differ only in some H-level resources that are renamed, but rules structures are identical. Hence, we can assume that the input can be performed by the i^{th} node of S_b . Again, by definition of (INPUT), we have that $\overline{\Sigma}'_b = \overline{\Sigma}_b[\Sigma'_{b,i}/\Sigma_{b,i}]$, with $\Sigma'_{b,i} = \Sigma_{b,i}[v_1/x_1 \dots v_k/x_k]$. Since $\overline{\Sigma}_a \equiv_L \overline{\Sigma}_b$ and states are updated in the same manner, we have that $\overline{\Sigma}'_a \equiv_L \overline{\Sigma}'_b$. The only problem may arise when upd contains resources that have been renamed: in this case S_b cannot update them. But renamed resources can only be H-level, hence they do not affect states L-equivalence. Since we remove from $\overline{\Theta}_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}_b$ a pair of updates primed equivalent, obtaining the sets of pools $\overline{\Theta}'_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}'_b$, we have that $\overline{\Theta}'_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}'_b$ are primed equivalent. Hence, it follows that $(S'_a, S'_b) \in \mathcal{R}$.

Case $\alpha = \text{upd} \triangleright T$. This action can be only derived by an application of the rule (STEP) of the AbU systems semantics (Fig. 1), where one of the nodes in S_a has applied the rule (EXEC) of the AbU node semantics (Fig. 1). Suppose that $\text{upd} = (x_1, v_1) \dots (x_k, v_k)$. We have three sub-cases, depending on the security level of the resources x_1, \dots, x_k .

Sub-case $\prod_{i \in [1..k]} \mathcal{P}(x_i) = \text{H}$. Then, we have that all resources in the update are H-level and, hence, $h_L(\alpha) = *$. By definition of AbU hiding bisimulation, α can always be mimicked by an arbitrary number (possibly 0) of hidden actions (i.e., labels β such that $h_L(\beta) = *$). Since $\overline{\Theta}_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}_b$ are primed equivalent, we can select $\beta = \text{upd}' \triangleright T'$ such that upd and upd' are primed equivalent. Hence, we can perform $S_b \xrightarrow{\beta}_H S'_b$, since $h_L(\beta) = *$. Note that, all resources in upd and upd' are H-level, so L-level resources are not modified, implying $\overline{\Sigma}'_a \equiv_L \overline{\Sigma}'_b$. Since we remove from $\overline{\Theta}_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}_b$ a pair of updates primed equivalent, obtaining the sets of pools $\overline{\Theta}'_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}'_b$, we have that $\overline{\Theta}'_a \equiv \overline{\Theta}'_b$. Hence, it follows that $(S'_a, S'_b) \in \mathcal{R}$.

Sub-case $\prod_{i \in [1..k]} \mathcal{P}(x_i) = \text{L}$ and $\bigsqcup_{i \in [1..k]} \mathcal{P}(x_i) = \text{H}$. Then, we have that at least one (but not all) resource in the update is L-level and, hence,

$h_L(\alpha) = \text{upd}|_L \neq \text{upd}$. Since $\overline{\Theta}_a \doteq \overline{\Theta}_b$, then there exists upd' in the i^{th} pool of $\overline{\Theta}_b$ such that upd and upd' are primed equivalent. Since, primed equivalent updates potentially differ on primed resources only and primed resources can only be H-level, we have that $\text{upd}'|_L = \text{upd}|_L$.

This implies that $h_L(\beta) = \text{upd}|_L$. Hence, we can perform $S_b \xrightarrow{\beta}_H S'_b$. Since in both systems only H-level resources are modified, we have that $\overline{\Sigma}'_a \equiv_L \overline{\Sigma}'_b$. Finally, since we remove from $\overline{\Theta}_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}_b$ a pair of updates primed equivalent, obtaining the sets of pools $\overline{\Theta}'_a$ and $\overline{\Theta}'_b$, we have that $\overline{\Theta}'_a \doteq \overline{\Theta}'_b$. Hence, it follows that $(S'_a, S'_b) \in \mathcal{R}$.

Sub-case $\prod_{i \in [1..k]} \mathcal{P}(x_i) = \text{H}$ and $\bigsqcup_{i \in [1..k]} \mathcal{P}(x_i) = \text{L}$. Then, we have that all resources in the update are L-level and, hence, we have that $h_L(\alpha) = \text{upd}|_L = \text{upd}$. Since $\overline{\Theta}_a \doteq \overline{\Theta}_b$ and upd does not contain primed resources, we have that S_b can perform the same update, i.e., upd is in the i^{th} pool of $\overline{\Theta}_b$. Hence, we can perform $S_b \xrightarrow{\alpha}_H S'_b$. Since both systems perform the same action, we trivially have that $\overline{\Sigma}'_a \equiv_L \overline{\Sigma}'_b$ and $\overline{\Theta}'_a \doteq \overline{\Theta}'_b$. Hence, it follows that $(S'_a, S'_b) \in \mathcal{R}$.

Proof of Theorem 5.2. We prove here the soundness of the proposed *safety* verification mechanism, namely that the syntactic transparency of Def. 5.1 implies the (semantic) transparency of Def. 4.5.

Theorem 5.2 (Soundness for Safety)

Proof. Assume that $\overline{R^S} \# \overline{R^R}$, i.e., $\text{snk}(\overline{R^S}) \cap \text{src}(\overline{R^R}) = \emptyset$, then we have to prove that for any $\overline{\Sigma} \in \text{comp}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R})$ we have that $\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}) \approx_{H_S} \text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$, where h_S maps labels of the form T and $\text{upd} \triangleright T$, with $\text{source}(\text{upd}) = \overline{R^S}$, to $*$; maps labels of the form $\text{upd} \triangleright T$, with $\text{source}(\text{upd}) \neq \overline{R^S}$, to $\text{upd} \triangleright T$; and maps labels of the form $\overline{\text{upd}} \blacktriangleright T$ to $\text{upd} \blacktriangleright T$. The proof is by contradiction.

Suppose that $\overline{R^S}$ is syntactically transparent for $\overline{R^R}$ but $\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}) \not\approx_{H_S} \text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$, for some $\overline{\Sigma}$. This means that it does not exist a AbU hiding bisimulation \mathcal{R} , parametric on H_S , that contains the pair $(\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}), \text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}))$. More precisely, by definition of bisimulation relation, whenever we try to build up a hiding bisimulation \mathcal{R} , parametric on H_S and containing the pair $(\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}), \text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}))$, the bisimulation game stops in a pair (S_a, S_b) , with S_a and S_b derivatives of $\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$ and $\text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$, respectively.

This because either: S_a can perform an action labeled α that cannot be (weakly) mimicked by S_b (or vice versa); or action mimicking is always possible but it leads us to pairs of the form (S'_a, S'_b) which do not belong to \mathcal{R} . Actually, since a bisimulation proof is a constructive procedure, we can always assume that the sought relation \mathcal{R} is large enough so that second case never applies.

Let $S_a = \text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}_a, \overline{\Theta}_a)$ and $S_b = \text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}_b, \overline{\Theta}_b)$, derivatives of $\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$ and $\text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$, respectively. We proceed by case analysis on the action α that would distinguish the two pairs S_a and S_b .

Case $\alpha = \text{upd} \blacktriangleright T$. This action can be only derived by an application of the rule (STEP) of the AbU systems semantics (Fig. 1), where one of the nodes

in S_a has applied the rule (INPUT) of the AbU node semantics (Fig. 1). However, this action denotes a modification of the resources made by an external entity. Thus, this action does not depend on the actual system and can always be performed both by S_a and S_b (we have to maintain fairness, i.e., external inputs have to be sent to both systems).

Case $\alpha = \text{upd} \triangleright T$. This action can be only derived by an application of the rule (STEP) of the AbU systems semantics (Fig. 1), where one of the nodes in S_a has applied the rule (EXEC) of the AbU node semantics (Fig. 1). We have two sub-cases, depending on the rules set that this node belongs to.

Sub-case $\text{source}(\text{upd}) = \overline{R^S}$. Then, we have that the node belongs to $\overline{R^S}$ and, hence, $h_S(\alpha) = *$. By definition of AbU hiding bisimulation, α can always be mimicked by an arbitrary number (possibly 0) of hidden actions (i.e., labels β such that $h_S(\beta) = *$).

Sub-case $\text{source}(\text{upd}) \neq \overline{R^S}$. Then, we have that the node belongs to $\overline{R^R}$ and, hence, $h_S(\alpha) = \text{upd} \triangleright T$. As α is the distinguishing action, it follows that the node reaches different states in S_a and S_b , leading to the following situation: the update upd is possible in S_a but not in S_b (or vice versa). Since both rule sets $\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}$ and $\overline{R^R}$ start in the same execution state set $\overline{\Sigma}$ (and with all pools empty), the rule set $\overline{R^R}$ could exhibit different behaviors if and only if it would be affected by $\overline{R^S}$. In particular, this means that in the execution trace leading from $\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$ to S_a , one rule in $\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}$ should have modified either: (i) a resource that a rule in $\overline{R^R}$ listens on; or (ii) a resource that is accessed by a rule in $\overline{R^R}$. Note that, the accessed resource not necessarily have to be used to assign other resources, it can be used into task condition, in order to modify the control flow. However, syntactic transparency $\overline{R^S} \#_c \overline{R^R}$, i.e., $\text{snk}(\overline{R^S}) \cap \text{src}(\overline{R^R}) = \emptyset$, is trivially preserved by all derivatives of the initial systems (rules do not ever syntactically change). This ensures that neither case applies.

As it does not exist a distinguishing action α , it follows that the original systems $\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$ and $\text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$ must be hiding bisimilar, i.e., $\text{sys}(\overline{R^S} \cup \overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma}) \approx_{H_S} \text{sys}(\overline{R^R}, \overline{\Sigma})$, where h_S maps labels of the form T and $\text{upd} \triangleright T$, with $\text{source}(\text{upd}) = \overline{R^S}$, to $*$; maps labels of the form $\text{upd} \triangleright T$, with $\text{source}(\text{upd}) \neq \overline{R^S}$, to $\text{upd} \triangleright T$; and maps labels of the form $\text{upd} \blacktriangleright T$ to $\text{upd} \blacktriangleright T$.

References

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